

The Hidden Life of the Classroom

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ABSTRACT

While digital technologies offer expanding opportunities for language learning beyond the classroom, the classroom itself remains a vital and complex site of language instruction. This article investigates the hidden dimensions of classroom life by examining the constructs of the *teacher self* and *learner self*. Drawing on research, classroom observations, and practitioner narratives, it explores how identity, beliefs, motivation, and agency shape engagement and interaction in language learning environments. Both the teacher self and the learner self are conceptualised in terms of identity, beliefs, and motivation. These constructs significantly influence classroom dynamics, pedagogical choices, and learning outcomes. The article advocates for reflective practices that enable educators to uncover and respond to these underlying dimensions, thereby enhancing teaching effectiveness and learner engagement. It offers practical insights for TESOL professionals seeking to better understand and support the evolving identities and motivations of both teachers and learners in diverse educational contexts.

Keywords: classroom dynamics, learner self, motivation, teacher identity, TESOL

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INTRODUCTION

Despite the growing availability of out-of-class learning opportunities through digital technologies, mobile devices, and media platforms, the classroom remains a central and enduring site for language instruction. Over the course of a career, a full-time teacher may spend between 30,000 and 40,000 hours in the classroom. Similarly, students typically accumulate approximately 900 instructional hours per year, amounting to over 11,000 hours between the ages of 5 and 18. These figures underscore the significance of classroom-based learning in shaping educational experiences. Language teaching and learning within the classroom are not solely cognitive processes; they are deeply embedded in social, emotional, and cultural dimensions. The classroom is a dynamic space where both teachers and learners bring their identities, beliefs, motivations, and histories into play. These personal and professional constructs influence how individuals engage in teaching and learning, as well as their perceptions of their roles in the classroom.

This article explores the *hidden life of the classroom* by examining how the constructs of the *teacher-self* and *learner-self* shape classroom engagement. It considers how identity, beliefs, and motivation influence pedagogical practices and learning outcomes, and argues for the importance of reflective inquiry in uncovering these often unseen dimensions of classroom life.

THE TEACHER SELF

The dimensions of teacher knowledge and practice explored here contribute to what can be called the *teacher self*—a complex and multidimensional construct encompassing a teacher's sense of identity, beliefs, values, emotions, experiences, motivation, professional knowledge, and personal history. These elements shape how teachers understand their role, how they perceive their students, the kind of teacher they aspire to be, and how they approach classroom instruction.

Sachs (2005) emphasises that teacher identity is not fixed but negotiated through experience and reflection. Bandura (2006) highlights the role of self-efficacy in shaping motivation and resilience in teaching. The distinction between the *open-self*, *secret-self*, *blind-self*, and *undiscovered-self* aligns with the Johari Window framework developed by Luft and Ingham (1955), which offers a lens for understanding self-awareness in interpersonal and professional contexts.

- The *open self* refers to aspects of a teacher's behaviour that are known both to the teacher and to others – that is, information that the teacher is willing and able to share with others. For example, 'I know that I often speak very quickly, and I sometimes ask students to signal to me when I am going too fast.'
- The *secret self* refers to information that is known to the teacher but not to others. For example, the teacher sometimes experiences stress and anxiety when teaching, but she does not want this to be obvious to others.
- The *blind self* refers to information that is known to others but not to the teacher. For example, the teacher may unintentionally spend more time with some students than others, resulting in unequal opportunities for all students to participate in the lesson.
- The *hidden self* refers to aspects of a teacher's identity and self-awareness that are unknown to both the teacher and to others. For example, neither the teacher nor others in the school may understand why the teacher is achieving lower-than-expected results with a new set of teaching materials.

In this article, I will focus on three aspects of the teacher self: teacher identity, teacher beliefs, and teacher motivation.

Teacher identity

We typically think of identity in relation to an individual's personal identity. *Personal identity* refers to unique and relatively stable features of a person's inner life that are performed or realised in contact and interaction with others. This image of the inner self, which a person presents to others, reflects features such as personality, age, gender, values, beliefs, life experience, self-image, or occupation, and depends on a person's role in an interaction—such as parent, son or daughter, friend, partner, customer, or student (Gee, 2000; Jenkins, 2008).

Teacher identity may reflect aspects of an individual's personal identity, but is primarily shaped by the nature of teaching itself. Teaching is a profession defined by the roles and functions teachers perform and the specialised knowledge and skills they bring to their work. As Pennington and Richards (2016) argue, teacher identity integrates personal, contextual, and professional factors and evolves through experience, reflection, and interaction within specific teaching contexts.

In the classroom, teachers enact a professional identity that may vary depending on the learners they teach. For instance, a teacher of young learners may adopt the role of storyteller or nurturer, while a teacher of adults may act as facilitator or motivator (Beijaard et al., 2004). These roles are not fixed but are shaped by pedagogical goals, institutional expectations, and the teacher's own beliefs and values. Teachers are expected to demonstrate attributes, such as commitment, subject knowledge, proficiency in English, and pedagogical skill. They are also expected to embody qualities such as warmth, confidence, enthusiasm, fairness, and emotional stability (Day et al., 2006). A teacher's professional identity is achieved and maintained through actions that may be both unconscious and strategic, as well as those that are consciously managed.

The teacher's proficiency in English is an important aspect of an English teacher's professional identity. A teacher whose English is not their dominant language may feel the need to maintain a strong command of English while teaching, which may require them to highlight different aspects of their professional identity than when teaching in their mother tongue.

I think the main problem in my teaching is my English. I do not have a natural ability to handle the language, so I very often have to stop, interrupt myself, and find the words. It's embarrassing. (Danish teacher)

I think my English proficiency is not good enough. I really want to do my best in every lesson. However, I often felt frustrated because I couldn't achieve my goals or meet the standards I had set before class. I always practised my English lessons before the class started because I did not want to lose face in front of my students. (Chinese student teacher)

Hence, more "identity work" may be needed to help the teacher realise the sense of academic authority that they have when teaching in their L1, and to be accepted by their students as a competent university lecturer or teacher.

TEACHER BELIEFS AND PRINCIPLES

Observing novice and experienced teachers was a regular aspect of my job when I worked as head of a large English department in a university. Hong Kong. Often, when I watched highly competent and experienced teachers teaching similar materials to similar classes of students, their classes functioned very differently. One reason for differences of this kind may be due to the different beliefs and

principles that individual teachers seek to realise in their teaching. Researchers refer to these as teachers' personal constructs of teaching, which shape how they approach their teaching. Shulman (1987) commented:

The final source of the knowledge base [of teaching] ... is the wisdom of practice itself, the maxims that guide or provide reflective rationalization for the practice of able teachers (p. 11).

What Shulman refers to as maxims are the working principles or beliefs that teachers consciously or unconsciously refer to as they teach. They are implicit theories about how students learn best and what makes for effective instruction. These can be inferred from observing how teachers conduct their lessons and from conversations with them about what they seek to achieve through their teaching. Wu and Richards (in press) examined Taiwanese EMI teachers' beliefs about the importance of English in their discipline and the type of language support they provided to their students. Significant differences were found between teachers' beliefs and practices in hard sciences, such as physics and engineering, and in soft subjects, such as history and education. Teachers in the hard sciences paid more attention to students' learning of content than to their use of English compared to teachers in the soft subjects. The former were also much more likely to use translanguaging in their teaching than soft subject teachers, who believed in the importance of providing an English-only language input to their students (See also Kao et al., 2021).

Teacher beliefs may be quite general (such as the idea that all lessons should connect to students' lives) or quite specific (such as the notion that peer error correction is more effective than teacher error correction). They may also be specific to a particular group of learners or to principles they seek to apply across all their teaching. An example of the former would be when a class contains students of very mixed levels, in which case the teacher seeks to realise these principles in her teaching:

- Vary group structures (pairs, small groups, whole class) to provide different learning contexts and opportunities for collaboration.
- Provide support and guidance to students who need it
- Set individualised learning goals for each student

A teacher I observed in Hong Kong described how her principles shaped her teaching:

As the years go by, I feel less of a 'teacher' and increasingly, a 'guide' or 'conductor', trying to extract what is inside my students: trying to give them courage and develop trust between themselves so that their learning experiences will be faster, easier and fun in the process. With that philosophy of a more humanistic approach behind me, I always strive to create lessons that foster communication and cooperation among learners, where I take a back seat and they rely on each other more – a more student-centred lesson. So, naturally, a successful lesson would have incorporated all of this – me as a guide, an example, initially, someone they can rely on for help and where I can slowly dissolve into the background while they are discussing in English the task they are doing, and where I reappear only to help encourage, and apologise for the lesson being over.

Teachers' personal principles profoundly influence their teaching and are shaped by their experience as teachers, professional development, and their own experiences as learners. The following examples (simulated by ChatGPT 4.0) show how differences in two teachers' beliefs lead to very different instructional choices when they teach:

Teacher A: -- A Communicative Approach

Beliefs:

- Language is best learned through communication.
- Making mistakes is part of learning.
- Students learn more when they are active and engaged.

Classroom Practices:

- Uses pair and group work regularly (e.g., information gap activities, role plays).
- Focuses on fluency over grammatical accuracy during speaking tasks.
- Uses authentic materials like news clips, podcasts, and menus.
- Encourages student talk time—she speaks less, so students speak more.
- Gives formative feedback rather than correcting every error.

Teacher B: – A Form-Focused Approach*Beliefs:*

- Accurate grammar and vocabulary are the foundation of language.
- Students need a clear structure and correction to improve.
- Learning is most efficient when guided step-by-step.

Classroom Practices:

- Begins lessons with explicit grammar instruction (e.g., rules of the past tense).
- Emphasises drills, repetition, and controlled practice before free use.
- Frequently uses textbooks and grammar exercises.
- Corrects spoken and written errors immediately.
- Uses tests and quizzes regularly to track progress.

The notion of teachers' beliefs and working principles needs to be kept in mind when you observe a teacher's class, because you may not be able to make sense of what happens during the lesson unless you clarify first with the cooperating teacher – the kinds of beliefs or principles that she seeks to realise in her teaching.

TEACHER MOTIVATION

Teacher motivation has been described as the energy that sustains and enhances teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and the overall educational environment (Han & Yin, 2016). It plays a crucial role in a teacher's job satisfaction, professional growth, and resilience in facing the challenges of the teaching profession (Klassen & Tze, 2014). Motivation influences not only instructional quality but also teacher retention, well-being, and the ability to adapt to changing educational demands. Some of its key attributes — commitment, self-esteem, agency, and self-efficacy — have been widely studied in recent literature.

Commitment refers to the teacher's personal engagement with teaching, the extent to which they have a sense of vocation, identify with and support the school's goals and practices and are willing to invest personal resources of time and energy to achieve excellence in teaching (Day et al., 2006).

I am a teacher. But I am not simply a teacher. I am an English, social studies, and math teacher, a teacher of teachers, and a student of teachers. I believe in and am committed to a just society, equity of outcomes, ongoing dialogue with students, and professionalism, as well as maintaining professional competency. I also value inquiry-based communities, high expectations, and thoughtful practice (Hsieh, 2010, p. 1)

An Australian-Brazilian English teacher at an Australian university cites in conversations with colleagues how her commitment to self-improvement is an important part of her teacher identity:

Actually, there is a bit of competition between the teachers regarding status; for example, the EAP teachers have a slightly higher status than the upper-intermediate teachers, and so on, even though that shouldn't be the case. As you know, I'm currently pursuing a PhD, and sometimes I can't help myself from saying 'in my research' in general staff room conversations, even though I know this isn't going to make anyone like me more. I guess it marks my status as a teacher who wants to improve themselves rather than one who is just getting by.

I think I have a sense of joy from being a teacher. I really hope I can do more as their teacher. I want to help them improve their test results, and I also want to be their friend. I want to take care of them and support them.

Self-esteem refers to an individual's attitudes towards themselves and the extent to which they believe themselves to be successful, competent, and of value to others (Howard & Johnson, 2004). Positive self-esteem contributes to a teacher's social competence, enabling effective communication with students and colleagues, and provides emotional support and job satisfaction, giving the teacher feelings of confidence and strong coping skills. Self-esteem also relates to the value, status and importance a teacher attributes to language teaching as a profession.

Whenever I have a conversation with someone, the peak of my pride and honour is when I introduce myself as a teacher. Unfortunately, many people take teachers for granted and don't value teaching as a profession. So, I try to be a positive representative of my profession.

Agency refers to the extent to which teachers can actively contribute to and manage change in their own teaching and professional development (Priestley et al., 2015). Rather than being the recipient of decisions and changes initiated by others, teacher agency is characterised by the teacher's ability to take ownership of their own learning and environment, and to set goals, develop curriculum, initiate change, and make decisions that affect the teacher's work and its conditions.

I like to try out new things in my teaching. To do so, I do take charge of my own learning and try to learn a new language using my own tips and techniques. This is a great way to experience what my learners go through on their language learning journey. Besides, by using this strategy, I get a lot of ideas of what works best for me as a basis for my future plans.

Self-efficacy refers to the teacher's view of his or her own effectiveness – that is, the ability to perform well as a teacher of English, to achieve their goals and potential, to maintain their commitment to teaching despite difficulties they may encounter and to provide support for students' learning (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). It is linked to positive teaching experiences. Teacher self-efficacy is linked to positive teaching experiences, such as observing students' progress and receiving positive feedback from students and others, which contributes to the teacher's sense of identity as a competent and successful educator. This, in turn, contributes to their sense of agency as well as their commitment to teaching.

I believe that to be effective, I have to inspire my students with the idea that their success in learning English will prepare them well for the future. This will also require more independent learning to achieve their goal. So, putting

the students on the right path is the key to my effectiveness and success as a teacher.

THE LEARNER SELF

By analogy with the notion of the *teacher self*, the *learner self* refers to how students perceive themselves as learners, encompassing their beliefs, identities, goals, motivations, emotions, and abilities. This concept encompasses learners' perceptions of language learning, their responses to the learning experience, their understanding of their role in classroom learning, and their management of both cognitive and emotional aspects of the learning process. Learners' perceptions of their own abilities and roles in the classroom shape their engagement, performance, confidence, and participation, which, in turn, influence their commitment to learning and their learning outcomes (Mercer, 2011; Dörnyei, 2009).

The learner self also involves the disposition learners have towards classroom learning and the kind of participation they favour. Research has shown that learners' self-concept—how they perceive their competence and identity as language users—is a central psychological construct that affects motivation and engagement (Mercer, 2011). For example, Mercer argues that self-concept is domain-specific and relatively stable, influencing learners' willingness to engage and persist in language learning tasks. Similarly, Sahinkarakas and Inozu (2017) found that learners' future L2 self-guides and vision significantly predict their ideal L2 self, which in turn drives motivation and classroom participation.

Moreover, learner identity is dynamic and socially constructed, shaped by intercultural experiences and classroom interactions. Poststructuralist perspectives in second language acquisition (SLA) emphasise that learners are active agents whose identities evolve through engagement with diverse linguistic and cultural contexts (Norton, 2013). This evolving identity influences learners' emotional responses—such as anxiety or enjoyment—and their willingness to communicate, which are critical to successful language learning (Dörnyei & Ryan, 2015).

Ultimately, emotional engagement and self-regulation are crucial components of the learner's self. Studies have shown that learners with high levels of grit and self-regulation exhibit stronger classroom engagement and better academic outcomes (Duckworth et al., 2007; Ushioda, 2011). Motivation and engagement, as

behavioural manifestations of the learner self, are influenced by learners' visions of themselves and their perceived autonomy, competence, and relatedness within the learning environment (Ryan & Deci, 2000). For example:

- *Relaxed or anxious*: Some learners may find the language class an opportunity to relax and enjoy themselves. For others, it may arouse anxiety, and they may be reluctant to participate.
- *Risk-taking or risk-avoiding*: Some students are not afraid to try new things, even if they may not be very successful. Others avoid activities that involve risks.
- *Playful or serious*: Some students enjoy activities that have a playful and fun element. Others think learning is serious business and may dislike such activities.
- *Fuzzy focused or black and white*: Some learners don't need clear outcomes for activities. Others prefer an unambiguous 'black-and-white' outcome.
- *Confident or insecure*: Some students have confidence in their abilities, while some may be less sure of their abilities.

As with the discussion of teacher self, I will consider the notion of learner self in relation to learner identity, learner beliefs, and learner motivation.

Learner identity

Learner identity involves the beliefs, values, and commitments an individual holds toward being a language learner (as distinct from other types of learners), as well as how others view their status as a language learner. It reflects the nature of interactions and their social context, and is considered an interactional achievement shaped by intent, power, and self-image (Norton, 2013; Block, 2007). This identity can significantly influence learners' attitudes and motivation toward English and language learning, their participation in classroom instruction, and their use of English beyond the classroom (Dörnyei & Ryan, 2015).

Learner identity is not static; it is dynamic, socially constructed, and often negotiated through interaction with others in various communities of practice (Pavlenko & Blackledge, 2004; Wenger, 1998). Learners bring particular identities to the classroom—such as being a mother, engineer, teenager, or

businessperson—but within the language classroom, these identities are often redefined, for example, as beginning, intermediate, or advanced-level learners. This redefinition is shaped by both internal perceptions and external positioning, including how learners are perceived by peers and teachers (Duff, 2012).

Poststructuralist perspectives in second language acquisition (SLA) emphasise that identity is multiple, fluid, and a site of struggle, changing over time and across contexts (Norton, 2013). Learners continuously negotiate their sense of self in relation to the social world, and this negotiation affects their investment in language learning. The concept of *investment*—as distinct from motivation—captures the socially and historically constructed relationship learners have with the target language and their desire to gain symbolic and material resources through language learning (Norton, 1995).

Furthermore, learner identity is closely tied to classroom dynamics and broader sociocultural contexts. Identity development is influenced by learners' sense of agency, their perceptions of affordances in the learning environment, and mismatches between imagined and practised communities (Kanno & Norton, 2003). In intercultural and study abroad contexts, identity conflicts—such as being positioned as a “foreigner”—can impact learners' engagement and acquisition of linguistic competence (Block, 2007). These experiences highlight the importance of viewing learners as active agents whose identities are co-constructed through interaction and shaped by power relations and cultural narratives (Pavlenko & Blackledge, 2004).

A learner's identity is defined by their interactions with the teacher and others, both in and out of the classroom. Lam (2000) documented an interesting identity transformation of a Chinese immigrant teenager through his electronic textual experiences. Whereas Almon was largely stigmatised as a low-achieving English as a second language student and struggled to develop English literacy in his school environment, his engagement with written English on the Internet with a transnational peer group in English allowed him to construct a more confident identity in this web-based context and to develop a sense of belonging to a global English-speaking community.

For some, the classroom may represent a site of struggle. Remaining silent is one way of protecting the learner's identity. A learner may be a highly motivated language learner but may nevertheless have little investment in the language practices of a given classroom, which may, for example, be racist, sexist, elitist, or

homophobic. Thus, despite being highly motivated, a learner could be excluded from classroom language practices and, over time, positioned as a 'poor' or unmotivated language learner.

Learner beliefs

Learner beliefs are the preconceived ideas or notions learners hold about different aspects of language and language learning. Learners may come to class with pre-formed ideas about how best to learn vocabulary or grammar, the kinds of people who do best at language learning, the importance of translation, the significance of a foreign accent, and the value of practice, repetition, error correction, and group work (Barcelos & Kalaja, 2011; Bernat & Gvozdenko, 2005). These beliefs are often shaped by prior learning experiences, cultural and educational backgrounds, and observations of teachers and peers. For example, some learners may hold stereotypical views such as 'girls are better at languages than boys', which reflect broader societal beliefs and can influence classroom dynamics and learner expectations (see also Bernat & Gvozdenko, 2005).

Learners may also have fixed ideas about the language they are studying. In the case of English, some may believe that certain varieties—such as British or American English—are superior to others, or that English has more or less grammar than other languages they have studied (Zhong, 2022). These beliefs can affect learners' attitudes toward different accents and dialects, and their openness to diverse forms of English. Additionally, learners set different goals for themselves in learning English. For some, native-like mastery is the ultimate goal, while others prioritise communicative competence and view localised use of English—including pronunciation features of their mother tongue—as a valid and culturally significant form of expression (Nguyen et al., 2014).

Importantly, learner beliefs are not static. They can evolve over time through reflection, interaction, and exposure to new learning contexts. Understanding and addressing learners' beliefs is crucial for teachers, as these beliefs influence learners' motivation, strategy use, and engagement with language tasks. Teachers and learners often hold differing beliefs about language learning, which can lead to curriculum misalignment. For instance, a teacher may value group work, while students may doubt their ability to learn through interactions with peers who have limited English proficiency. Or when students come from a culture where rote learning and memorisation are widely used and considered useful strategies for learning English, whereas the teacher does not believe in their value and tries to

discourage learners from using them. Students may also have very specific views and expectations about what they expect of a teacher, as we see in these comments from Australian students:

A good teacher is someone who can persuade other people to express themselves and bring out the creativity in kids. I think everyone has creativity they don't use, and it's the teacher's ability to bring that out in the person and persuade them to use it.

The ultimate thing for a teacher is the ability and willingness to sit down and talk to students, because you find that some English teachers (they're in a minority) aren't willing to talk to their students on a level...; you get people who talk down which is the worst thing for the writing of English because you need to be able to discuss things absolutely straight.

Learners may also have different views about the goals and purpose of different kinds of classroom activities. In the case of reading, for example, in the same class of young learners, students may have different beliefs about the nature and purpose of reading:

- *Reading is saying words correctly:* The focus is on saying words aloud. Reading is a performance of calling out words.
- *Reading is schoolwork:* Reading is just another assignment to be completed before moving on to something more enjoyable. It is not something they would normally choose to do on their own.
- *Reading is a source of status:* It is an activity to be announced and performed in front of the class.
- *Reading is a way to learn things:* Reading is studying, and they choose to read things that contain interesting and important information.
- *Reading is a private pleasure:* Children read things that have personal meaning for them.
- *Reading is a social activity:* Reading is a shared activity conducted collaboratively in pairs or groups. It is a source of pleasure with friends.

When classes consist of students from different cultures or when the teacher does not share the same linguistic and cultural background as the students, some students may find that the norms for classroom learning in the English lesson are different from those in their own culture, reflecting different beliefs about the nature of good teaching, as we see in these comments.

The trouble with Chinese teachers is that they've never done any real teacher-training courses, so they don't know how to teach. All they do is follow the book. They never give us any opportunity to talk. How in the world do they expect us to learn? (Australian student studying in China)

Australian teachers are very friendly but they can't teach very well. I never know where they're going – there's no system and I just get lost. Also, they're often poorly trained and lack a thorough grasp of their subject. (Chinese student studying in Australia, Brick, 2004)

Many Asian learners are also familiar with a teaching approach influenced by Confucian educational values and may initially be resistant to the learner-centred approach used in other countries. They may tend to view teachers as authority figures, which differs from how they are perceived in Western culture. When I started teaching in the US after many years in Asia, I was surprised that many students used my first name without being invited to do so. Whereas some former students of mine in Thailand who are now university professors still insist on using the honorific *ajarn* and feel uncomfortable calling me by my first name.

Learners may have to accommodate a different set of assumptions about the nature of classroom communication from those operating in their home culture. This may mean adopting new ways of interacting that reflect different norms for interpersonal communication, particularly in the pragmatic domain—such as differences in degrees of taciturnity, including the keeping of one's thoughts and emotions to oneself, as well as issues of control, reserve, reticence, self-restraint, and communicativeness (Scollon et al., 2012; Yates & Nguyen, 2012). These differences are often rooted in culturally specific expectations about appropriate behaviour and communication, which can affect learners' comfort and participation in classroom discourse.

The learner's view of what constitutes a "good learner" may also differ from the teacher's, leading to resistance toward classroom behaviours that conflict with their cultural identity. For example, learners from cultures that value humility—such as Japanese or Chinese students—may avoid speaking English in front of their

classmates to prevent being perceived as “showing off” (Cortazzi & Jin, 1996; Jin & Cortazzi, 2006). This reluctance to speak publicly is often discussed in terms of “willingness to communicate” (WTC), a concept widely studied in Chinese EFL contexts. Research shows that Chinese learners may experience speaking anxiety and reticence due to cultural norms that discourage overt self-expression, especially in group settings (Peng, 2012; Wen & Clement, 2003).

Such resistance is not merely behavioural but reflects deeper identity negotiations. Learners may resist classroom practices they perceive as misaligned with their cultural values or personal identity, particularly when power dynamics and classroom positioning challenge their sense of self (Norton, 2013). Creating inclusive classroom environments that affirm learners’ cultural identities and respect diverse communication styles can help mitigate these tensions and foster more meaningful engagement (Kramersch, 1993).

Motivation

Motivation is often described as the driving force of second language learning, and without a strong desire to learn English, learners are unlikely to invest the time and effort required (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011; Gardner, 2010). Students with a strong interest in learning English may view it as having “capital” or potential value. Their motivation may reflect different values they associate with proficiency in English, such as academic achievement, future job opportunities, communication through social media, cross-cultural friendships, participation in popular culture through movies, television, and pop music, international travel, the opportunity to develop an international outlook, and the prestige associated with bilingual fluency in English (Norton, 2013; Ushioda, 2017).

Dörnyei (2009) proposed that learners can be motivated by an imagined view of themselves—a vision of the person they would like to become—and that mastery of English is a core component of this possible self, functioning as a powerful motivational tool. His L2 Motivational Self System includes three components: the ideal L2 self (who the learner wants to become), the ought-to L2 self (who others expect the learner to become), and the L2 learning experience (the learner’s immediate learning environment). These components have been shown to significantly predict learners’ intended effort and engagement in language learning.

Classroom learning conditions can do a great deal to maintain learners’ motivation. Lessons that are motivating for students contain purposeful activities at an

appropriate level; they are not overloaded with content; they promote learner involvement and engagement; and they give learners a sense of success rather than failure (Dörnyei & Csizér, 1998). This reflects what is sometimes referred to as the **Goldilocks Rule**, which suggests that peak motivation occurs when learners are working on tasks that are “just right”—not too easy and not too hard, but at the edge of their current abilities. In a similar sense, both Kagan (1990) and Treffers-Daller (2024) use the term *Goldilocks* to describe the need for the appropriate amount of something—whether in the complexity of ideas or the proportion of language use in learning—highlighting the importance of balance for effective engagement and learning.

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy refers to the learner’s view of their own effectiveness—that is, their belief in their ability to succeed in learning English, achieve their goals and potential, and maintain their commitment to learning English despite difficulties they may encounter (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy is closely linked to the learner’s positive experiences in learning English and plays a critical role in shaping their motivation, persistence, and performance (Chang et al., 2024). Learners with high self-efficacy are more likely to engage actively in language learning tasks because they believe their efforts will lead to success. They are more willing to take risks, such as speaking in class or using the language outside the classroom, and they tend to persist longer when faced with challenges (Cai, 2024).

Moreover, self-efficacy is not a fixed trait—it can be developed through mastery experiences, observing others succeed (vicarious experiences), receiving encouragement (verbal persuasion), and managing emotional states (Bandura, 1986). In second language contexts, self-efficacy has been shown to be a strong predictor of performance across language skills, including speaking, writing, and listening. It also mediates the relationship between learners’ motivation and their actual achievement, making it a key factor in successful language acquisition.

Whenever I saw a tourist, I would try my best not to be shy and talk to them. This talking to strangers happened mostly on Yahoo Messenger when chatting with people around the world. (Hamed)

But I think I learned more through communicating with foreigners. I often approached foreigners I met to speak with them. (Vida)

Chilian student Danilo has started to learn German, and described how he makes use of Instagram to learn through interaction with other learners of German:

I created an Instagram account in which I only followed profiles that posted content for learning German and many other topics, all in German. By scrolling through social media in German every day, I am absorbing German vocabulary and grammar. At first, it was quite tough, but after about a month and a half, I started being able to understand most of what I read, and I can also understand the structure of the language as well. I also complement this with web research and the use of ChatGPT to learn basic conversation and phrases.

High self-efficacy helps learners persist through difficulties, such as understanding grammar or pronunciation, and contributes to resilience in the face of setbacks, reducing the likelihood of giving up (Bandura, 1997). Learners with strong self-efficacy are more likely to use effective learning strategies, such as seeking feedback, practising outside of class, and employing metacognitive strategies, such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning (Chang et al., 2024). These learners tend to approach challenges with confidence and are more proactive in managing their learning.

When learners believe they can succeed, they experience less language anxiety, especially in speaking and listening contexts. Self-efficacy has been shown to buffer against anxiety by fostering a sense of control and competence in communication tasks (Wang, 2024). Research consistently shows that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of actual performance in second language learning—often more so than aptitude or prior achievement (Mills, Pajares, & Herron, 2007; Pérez Navío et al., 2024). This makes self-efficacy a critical factor in both the cognitive and emotional dimensions of language acquisition.

Agency

Agency refers to the extent to which learners can actively contribute to and manage change in their own learning, act independently, and make choices about their learning (Duff, 2012; Mercer, 2011). It positions learners not as passive recipients of knowledge but as active participants in the learning process. This is reflected in their motivation and engagement: learners with a strong sense of agency are more likely to set goals, persist through challenges, and take initiative, resulting in more sustained engagement with the language (Ushioda, 2011).

Learners with agency often create personalised learning paths by seeking methods and resources that suit their interests and learning styles—for example, listening to music, watching TV shows, or engaging in conversation to develop language skills (Lamb, 2017). They look for opportunities beyond the classroom and develop a sense of autonomy, often acquiring skills in self-monitoring, reflection, and self-correction (Benson, 2013). This autonomy enables them to take responsibility for their own progress rather than relying solely on teachers, fostering a deeper, more meaningful learning experience (Little, 2007).

Danilo, the Chilean student I referred to earlier, experienced his introduction to English in a very similar way to the examples of traditional classroom teaching cited above. Finding that he was learning very little from it, he took matters into his own hands. For him, the three most useful activities for learning English were watching TV shows and movies, watching YouTube clips, and learning songs. On the value of watching movies, he commented:

TV and movies help the most because there's plenty of dialogue between characters, and they usually speak correctly. If they have a different way of speaking, it is always noticeable which group the person comes from, which helps learning as well.

Danilo added:

In Chile, my country, English taught in school is usually not useful at all, unless you go to an English private school, because you can be surrounded by it every day, all day, but other than that, even in an English after-school Institute, it is very likely that you come out of it knowing very little. Everyone I know here in Chile who speaks English, including myself, has learned on their own by immersing themselves in the language and by being willing to learn. I think what's the most important and helped me the most was that I would speak with myself, or try to think in English and use the words I learned for expressing things that happened around me, even though if I didn't have the need to, or I wasn't talking to anybody, so that the language would become a part of me.

CONCLUSIONS

We could say that the person you see at the tennis club becomes a different person when they step into the classroom as a teacher—their *teacher self* takes over. Similarly, the student you see enjoying a movie with friends becomes a different person when they enter the classroom—their *learner self* emerges. These shifts reflect the dynamic, context-dependent nature of identity, in which individuals enact different selves depending on the social setting and expectations (Gee, 2025; Norton, 2013).

Observing the lessons of experienced teachers is a regular activity in teacher education programs, and many forms of lesson observation have been developed to guide the process. These often include categories of teacher and learner performance such as the procedures the teacher used to scaffold lessons, the kinds of questions teachers asked, the amount of teacher talk and student talk, how group work was set up, the kinds of feedback provided, and the learners' use of English during the lesson. To ensure objectivity, observation forms and protocols generally focus on low-inference categories—observable and quantifiable actions that do not require interpretation or subjective judgment (Barkhuizen, 2016).

However, many of the features discussed above—such as beliefs, motivations, and identity—are high-inference aspects of the teacher and learner self. These are not easily captured through a single lesson observation. As Gee (2015) and Olsen et al. (2023) argue, identity is enacted through language, behaviour, and values, and

often includes elements that may be open, secret, blind, or undiscovered. Understanding these deeper dimensions requires sustained engagement with classroom life and reflective practice over time.

For teachers, exploring and understanding the nature and impact of the teacher self can occur through critical reflection, self-observation (e.g., video analysis), peer observation, case studies, reflection on critical incidents, and group-based reflective activities (Farrell, 2015; Zarrabi & Mohammadi, 2024). These practices help teachers uncover the values, beliefs, and motivations that shape their professional identity and teaching practice. Similarly, learners can reflect on their identities, beliefs, and learning experiences through narrative writing, classroom discussions, and the construction of personal stories about their journey as language learners (Miyahara, 2015). Such reflective practices foster greater self-awareness and agency, enabling both teachers and learners to engage more meaningfully in the educational process.

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